

MicrogridSpy Analysis for Electrification of Kalibote Village in Mozambique

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Energy Modelling Platform Africa (EMP-A)

2025

Context

- Pop 2024: 33 244 414
- Electricity Access Rate: 60.1%
Urban elec. Rate : 50,5%
Rural elec. rate: 9,6%

Total Installed Capacity: 3 153 MW

Challenges

Policy Framework	Challenges
National Electrification Strategy, 2018	Around 40% of the population has no access to electricity. It is estimated that 70% of the population will be connected to REN by 2030 and the remaining 30% will be served by a combination of mini-grids and SHS.
Electrification Plan for Off-Grid Areas, Resolution n.º 52/2023	Increasing private sector participation through least-cost electrification solutions.
Energy Transition Strategy, Resolution n.º 61/2023	Accelerating the expansion of access to electricity through clean and sustainable sources.

Main Research Questions

- Select the best Technology combination to electrify Kalibote Village?
- How much investment might be needed?

To model the energy needs, Microgridspy was used, an open-source energy optimization tool developed to assist in the planning, sizing, and operation of rural and off-grid microgrids, particularly in remote or underserved areas.

User Category	Appliances															
	Indoor & Outdoor Bulbs	Torch Flashlight	Phone Charger	TV	Decorder	Refrigerator	Freezer	POS	Laptop	Printer	Hair Clippers	Hair Dryer	Pub Lights	Fan	Iron	Air Extractor
Low Income	●	●	●													
Lower Middle Income	●	●	●	●	●	●								●	●	
School	●		●						●	●						
Barba Shop	●	●	●								●	●				
Shop	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●						●		
Milling Machine	●		●											●	●	●
Public Lighting													●			

Output from Demand Assessment

Average Daily Demand Profile - 2025

Output from Demand Assessment

Average Daily Demand Profile - 2029

3% increase from year 1 to year 5

Scenario definition

Scenarios	System	Constrain	Load
Scenario 1	PV Battery Generator	No Renewable Penetration Constraint	Partial Load activated
Scenario 2	PV Battery Generator	Minimum Renewable Penetration: 95%	Partial Load activated
Scenario 3	PV Battery	100% Renewable	

Results - Average Energy Usage by Technology

Scenario 1

Scenario 2

Scenario 3

■ Solar PV ■ Battery ■ Diesel Generator

■ Solar PV ■ Battery ■ Diesel Generator

■ Solar PV ■ Battery

Results

Conclusions and Policy Insights

Among the three scenarios investigated, the PV+Battery+Diesel Generator option, with an investment cost of 59,22 kUSD and a LCOE of 0.3992 USD/kWh, emerges as the most financially favourable solution. In contrast, the PV+Battery option entails a significantly higher investment cost of 232,83 kUSD and a LCOE of 0.7088 USD/kWh.

From scenario 1 to 3, there is an Increased Solar Integration: Solar PV's share rises from 61.2% to 68.7%, showing a trend toward greater renewable penetration. **Diesel Phase-Out:** The gradual elimination of the diesel generator from 26.3% down to 0% reflects the policy goals of the Government of Mozambique for decarbonization of the energy sector and Battery usage remains relatively stable (~31–61%), underlining its importance in enabling high renewable penetration by storing excess solar energy and stabilizing supply.

Future Work

Currently developing the Least Cost Electrification Plan, which is a high-level approach, when its concluded, there will be a need to go deeper on the analysis of the selected locations with Microgridspy.

MUITO OBRIGADO

THANK YOU